

METHODS OF TEACHING GRAMMAR IN ENGLISH SYSTEM

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Abstract. *This article provides useful information about the methods of teaching grammar in english system. This article aims to expand your knowledge about grammar education.*

Key words: *grammar education, methods, methodical recommendations, knowledge skills.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ГРАММАТИКЕ В СИСТЕМЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена полезная информация о методах обучения грамматике в системе английского языка. Эта статья направлена на расширение ваших знаний об обучении грамматике.*

Ключевые слова: *грамматическое образование, методика, методические рекомендации, знания, навыки.*

Public institutions everywhere have been preaching the concept of grammar for years, yet for some mystical reason, society cannot seem to figure it out. If one is truly honest about the topic, he or she will have to admit that the collective grammar of this country is simply tragic. Into whose lap does this task fall? English teachers. Teaching English grammar to a group of students is a job that should grant super human status to any teacher who manages to do it successfully. There is a steaming buffet of options to pick from when it comes to choosing the best way to teach this age old and ever-relevant area of study.

There is the new-age method of teaching grammar, which ironically doesn't actually teach grammar at all, but instead hopes students just sort of "pick it up" as they read different texts; then, there is a method somewhere in the middle, the "discuss some grammatical concept in a mini-lesson format, then analyze that concept as students read and write" method. Each method depends on who is doing the teaching, what kind of students occupy the classroom, and the demands of the school system, and each method has plenty to smile about and sneer upon. The traditional method of teaching grammar is still very popular among experienced teachers and teachers that have been in the profession for a while.

Everyone knows these kinds of teachers. They proclaim this world has gone to the deepest pits of hell in the roughest of hand baskets, and truly the rest of the teachers wonder why they are still teaching at all. There are a few young, fresh, braves who enter the teaching field and follow the example set by their teachers in high school-- the traditional, grammar book, worksheet, right or wrong example. Regardless of whether they look at the student population and see the wasting away of society or a field of young and potential-filled flowers, these teachers see grammar as something that should be taught in isolation.

It should be given its own time, its own unit, and its own space in the curriculum. Not incorrectly, they see their chosen field of study as something so highly important that it cannot be ignored nor tainted with other subjects; the students must learn it because, well, that's what students do: they learn grammar. Well, there may be one fact these traditionalists are overlooking when it comes to teaching grammar. Why is it that students, when taught grammar the

traditional, isolated way, have to be re-taught the same grammatical concepts year after year? It seems to the common observer that they're simply not learning it. They remember the concepts for the worksheet and the test but soon forget and have to learn the next year. There is certainly something awry in this system. Are teachers wasting their time trying to fill young minds with grammatical facts? If they're not, then why do so many adults who have graduated high school and gone through years of repetitive grammar instruction display horrific grammatical skills. Based on this information, many have decided to abandon the practice of teaching grammar all-together.

They have brushed it off as worthless and have instead chosen to cross their fingers in hopes that if students read enough and write enough, they will start to naturally see the patterns of the English language. For some students this may work. In fact, it may work for many students. However, teachers may collide into a problem with this system. In every state, teachers have a curriculum to follow, a list of "to-do's". These curriculum lists usually contain a set of pure grammatical skills that the students must learn, and unless the teacher wants to rebel against the curriculum that teacher must teach those things, the endless dilemmas of the English teachers would arise. For those teachers who are neither traditional nor rebellious, there is a middle road of grammar instruction.

This type of instruction combines grammar with reading and writing as an everyday experience in the classroom. This method is very much dependent on the teacher's creativity and his or her ability to weave grammar into every other area of the English classroom. It is by no means the easiest way to teach grammar, but as research has shown, it may be the most effective. It is definitely the method that takes the most time and creativity on the part of the teacher, but for a dedicated professional, these are both secondary concerns to the level of learning the students achieve. There are teachers who make the traditional method work; somehow they have found a way to get bits of information to implant themselves into student minds like tiny eggs of precious information.

There are teachers who don't handle grammar at all, but they make their students read enough and write enough that somehow they pass their state tests and grow up with a basic knowledge of the concepts; and there are teachers who creatively combine grammar to other classroom activities. Learning and teaching grammar requires some creativity in order to make learning grammar a communicative process (The way to learn is to do. Learn by doing. Doing is learning). So this would depend the grammar structure you are targeting, the learners' level, and what "learning grammar" means to the learner. Traditional method book exercises and worksheets are, also, helpful. A multi-faceted approach is practical. Grammar should be part of an integrated approach. Of course, there is any number of ways to consider an integrated approach. And, also, grammar items should not be taught in isolation.

They can be, but in rigidly adhering to doing just one thing at a time. A target structure or target structures indicate direction and focus but other things may come up along the way and there's no sense, of course, in ignoring them. Speaking is primary, and learning to use grammar should be integrated with speaking practice. Combine functions of language with grammar instruction. Still grammar requires some separate attention and focus apart from everything else in order to ensure a solid understanding. What is "modern" outside of an integrative approach which has a strong focus on grammar as a base and facilitating conversation in learning

vocabulary, tenses, and sentence structure? Most grammatical errors of non-native speakers of English would not be found among native speakers of English. Non-native speakers of English require explicit instruction in grammar forms, the meaning of those forms, and how and when to use the forms. Native speakers of English don't require this A point of instruction that may be common to both non-native speakers of English and native speakers of English would be utilizing the variety of grammatical form, combined with lexical choices, to produce better writing or to be a more articulate speaker. However, even for this purpose, the needs of native speakers and non-native speaker would not always be in alignment.

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